

Aerothermal analysis of Themis T3: influence of nozzle cluster geometry on the base heating and heat loads on the grid fins

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SALTO project – Themis T3 configuration

- The Horizon Europe project SALTO (reusable Strategic Space Launcher Technologies & Operations) directly supports ESA's Themis program by testing key technologies for reusable launchers.
- Themis T3 is a reference configuration for a future Vertical Takeoff Vertical Landing (VTVL) demonstrator, design for suborbital flights.
- It uses retro propulsion combined with Aerodynamic Control Surfaces (ACS) to achieve a smooth touch-down.

Main goals of this work

Main goals:

- Discuss typical flow field topologies and resulting heating patterns for critical phases of the ascent and re-entry flight with a focus on the base area and aerodynamic control surfaces.
- Assess the role of nozzle cluster geometry and gas generator exhaust on the base heating.

Addressed by:

- Comprehensive set of CFD analyses.
- Generation of surrogate models (aerothermal databases) to efficiently assess loads during the entire trajectory.

Numerical model & CFD Mesh

- DLR TAU-Code: 2nd-order FV Navier-Stokes
- Spalart-Allmaras low-Re RANS-model
- Nozzle exhaust from internal flow path analysis (Chemical non equilibrium, skeletal Slavinskaya mechanism 20 species and 237 reactions)
- Chemical non equilibrium, global Westbrook and Dryer mechanism 10 species and 3 reactions
- Isothermal walls ($T_w=200, 600K$)
- $AoA=0^\circ$, Quarter configuration - Structured/unstructured mesh

Ascent (2.4M points)

Re-entry (16.6M points)

Ascent trajectory: low altitude mode

CFD	Mach [-]	h/h_{max} [-]
3 eng	1.1	0.114

- The heat flux is dominated by flow recirculation in the near field

- The forebody turbulent boundary layer separates at the base plate shoulder, hits the hot nozzle exhaust and brings heated gas back in the bubble

Ascent trajectory: low altitude mode

Gas generators impact on the base heating

- The presence of gas generators significantly changes the topology of the flow field in the base region and consequently the heat flux pattern on the base plate and nozzle walls
- When the gas generators are on, the heat flux distribution is extremely nonuniform and the peak value is much higher
- The position on the base plate where the heat peak occurs varies considerably over time

Ascent trajectory: high altitude mode

CFD	Mach [-]	h/h_{\max} [-]
3 eng	2.8	0.57

- Stronger plume-plume interactions occurs in the base area leading to a recirculation of hot exhaust gases between the nozzle clusters.

- The exhaust back flow leaves a mark on the heat flux pattern on the base plate

Ascent trajectory: high altitude mode

Gas generators impact on the base heating

- The heating pattern is very different between the two cases.
- When the gas generators are active, the peak value is considerably higher.

Ascent trajectory

Time evolution of average heat flux

- The time history of the average heat flux on the nose is not affected by the presence of GG
- Significant impact of GG exhaust on nozzle wall and base plate (only for $T_w=600K$)

Nose

Baseplate

Nozzles

Ascent trajectory

Base flow modes transition

- Unlike in the RETALT project, the transition between low and high altitude mode is gradual -> no sharp jump in the average heat flux.
- This feature may be due to the different geometry of the nozzle cluster

Re-entry trajectory

Retro-burn beginning: aft bay

CFD	Mach [-]	h/h_{\max} [-]
2 eng	3	0.168

- Most critical phase in terms of heat fluxes
- Flow field topology never observed before

Re-entry trajectory

Retro-burn beginning: grid fins

- Large heat fluxes are observed at the leading edge ($q/q_{nose\ max} = 62$) and on the support structures, which are directly exposed to the hot exhaust gases. The heat flux drops dramatically along the thickness.
- The grid fin operates in choked mode under the current flight conditions

Re-entry trajectory

Time evolution of average heat flux

- Similar qualitative trend regardless of the imposed wall temperature and the component under study.
- The average heat flux increases during the aerodynamic phase prior to retro-propulsion, reach the maximum at the beginning of the maneuver and then decrease again due to the reduction in flight velocity

Concluding remarks

- During the ascent, thermal loads generally remain small. Depending on the altitude two characteristic base flow modes can be identified. Unlike other projects, there is no clear transition between the two modes, which may be due to the different geometry of the nozzle cluster.
- The presence of secondary (gas generator) exhaust has a significant impact on the hot gas recirculation and can substantially increase baseplate and nozzle walls thermal loads.
- The retro burn maneuver turns out to be the most critical phase in terms of thermal loads on the aft bay, nozzles outer wall and grid fins.
- The choice to use two engines for retro-propulsion and the free stream conditions at the beginning of the maneuver create a rather peculiar flow field structure that imposes severe thermal loads on the structure.

Thanks for the attention!

Ascent trajectory

Time evolution of peak heat flux

